

Notas breves

Epitonium brevissimum (G. Seguenza, 1876) (Caenogastropoda, Epitoniidae): new records in the Tyrrhenian Sea and the Strait of Gibraltar

Epitonium brevissimum (G. Seguenza, 1876) (Caenogastropoda, Epitoniidae): nuevas citas en el mar Tirreno y estrecho de Gibraltar

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INTRODUCTION

Epitonium brevissimum was described by G. SEGUENZA (1876) as a fossil from the Pliocene of southern Italy and reported from the Pliocene of Capo Milazzo (PALAZZI AND VILLARI, 1996). A shell was subsequently found in a collection by Seguenza in the Geological and Paleontological Museum of Florence University (BERTOLASO AND PALAZZI, 2000).

The shell is easily recognizable by its shape: the teleoconch is somewhat globose, trochiform, of about two very convex whorls crossed by close-set fragile lamellae. The aperture is circular. The umbilicus is wide. The shell is uni-

formly dirty white in colour. The protoconch is subcylindrical with a narrow light brown subsutural band (PEÑAS, ROLÁN, LUQUE, TEMPLADO, MORENO, RUBIO, SALAS, SIERRA AND GOFAS, 2006; GOFAS, MORENO AND SALAS, 2011). The animal is unknown.

Three shells were recently found on coralligenous bottoms of Alboran island (80-200 m) while one fresh shell is reported from the Celtic Sea off Brittany (313-330 m) (both in PEÑAS ET AL., 2006). No further records are known. Three new findings for the Mediterranean Sea are reported in this note.

TAXONOMY

Family EPITONIIDAE Berry S.S., 1910

Genus *Epitonium* Röding, 1798

Epitonium brevissimum (G. Seguenza, 1876) (Fig. 1 A-C)

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Figure 1. *Epitonium brevisimum* (Seguenza G., 1876). A: specimen from Capraia Island (Tuscan Archipelago (Tuscany, Italy) (H=1.47 mm); B, C: specimen from Punta Marroquí (Tarifa, Spain) (H=1.87 mm), apertural and apical views.

Figura 1. *Epitonium brevisimum* (Seguenza G., 1876). A: concha de la isla de Capraia (Archipiélago Toscano, Toscana, Italia) (H= 1,47 mm); B, C: concha de Punta Marroquí (Tarifa, España) (H= 1,87 mm), vistas abertural y apical.

Material examined: 1 shell off Vibo Valentia (Calabria, Italy), 1999, 200 m depth, in a sediment sample trawled by local fishermen, in A. Pagli collection; 1 shell off Capraia Island, Tuscan Archipelago (Tuscany, Italy), 1999, 200 m depth, in a sediment sample trawled by local fishermen, in C. Bogi collection (Fig. 1 A); 1 shell from Punta Marroquí (Tarifa, Spain) by the local lighthouse, 07-07-2012, 39 m depth, in a shell grit sample collected by SCUBA diving, in A. Raveggi collection (Fig. 1 B-C); 1 shell from the same locality, date and collector, 40 m depth, in a shell grit sample, in A. Raveggi collection.

Morphological features: Morphological features for the studied shells are summarized in Table I.

Discussion: The Tyrrhenian shells as well as those from the Alboran Sea do not look fresh and possibly are from Pleistocene thanatocoenoses. No living populations seem to actually occur in the Mediterranean Basin.

The shells from Tarifa, although without soft parts, are doubtless recent. They confirm the species presence in North East Atlantic but widely extend its range southward up to the Mediterranean border. Moreover they were found at shallower depths than previous records, showing that the species has a wider bathymetry. Unfortunately, no hypothesis can be made about the species host. Further research and the eventual discovery of live specimens may give more accurate information on *E. brevisimum* biology and ecology.

Epitonium iberomicroscopicum Landau, La Perna and Marquet, 2006, described from the Early Pliocene of Estepona (Southern Spain), is an allied species only known from the holotype. Unfortunately LANDAU, LA PERNA AND MARQUET (2006, p. 27, pl. 8, fig. 4) did not compare the new species with *E. brevisimum* but with *E. nanum* (Jeffreys, 1884) and *E. pseudonanum* Bouchet and Warén, 1986. Although very similar to *E. brevisimum* some differences can be recognized: *E. iberomicroscopicum* has only a very narrow umbilical chink, a more conical profile and more dense lamellae. The true significance of these differences will be better assessed when new material is available for study; meanwhile we prefer to keep them distinct. LANDAU ET AL. (2006) also commented that the new species has been found in Pleistocene bathyal beds from Sicily, but we suspect that this record could be attributed to *E. brevisimum*.

Table I. Morphological features of examined shells. H = maximum height (in mm); h = height of aperture (in mm); hp = height of protoconch (in μm); nlw = number of lamellae on body whorl; nwp = number of whorls of protoconch; nwt = number of whorls of teleoconch; W = maximum width (in mm).

Tabla I. Características morfológicas de las conchas estudiadas. H= altura máxima (en mm); h= altura de la abertura (en mm); hp= altura de la protoconcha (en μm); nwt= número de vueltas de la teleoconcha; nlw= número de láminas axiales en la última vuelta; nwp= número de vueltas de la protoconcha; nwt= número de vueltas de la teleoconcha; W= anchura máxima (en mm).

Shells	H	h	hp	W	nwt	nwp	nlw
A	1.65	0.80	330	1.32	2.1	3.2	40
B	1.47	0.72	315	1.30	2.0	3.0	40
C	1.87	0.86	380	1.52	2.4	3.0	38
D	0.95	0.48	385	0.82	1.2	2.9	40

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